

Energy Sector Modeling for Regional Analysis with OSeMOSYS

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Executive Summary

A key part of this transition is the development of a methodological approach to harmonize diverse energy matrices across the region. This approach involves a systematic workflow that includes manual preprocessing of country-specific data, integration into the OSeMOSYS model framework using Python, and subsequent data organization and processing. The strategic expansion of this energy integration model is planned to occur in phases, starting with Colombia and Ecuador due to their geographical proximity, and eventually encompassing the entire Latin American and Caribbean region. The results of this approach have shown notable growth in renewable energy sectors, especially in onshore wind technology in countries like Colombia, despite a continued reliance on coal. Ecuador, on the other hand, displays a more balanced expansion across various renewable technologies. However, the approach faces challenges like limited hardware capacity and a dependence on commercial solvers, pointing to the need for continued development and refinement of methodologies and tools in energy system analysis.

1. Introduction

The energy sector in Latin America is undergoing a significant transition. While natural gas has been a primary energy source, there is a notable shift towards the increased adoption of renewable energy sources such as wind, solar, geothermal, and small-scale hydro power plants [1]. This transition is coupled with sustainability efforts, including initiatives to reduce energy losses in the grid, electrify end uses, and the planned construction and phase-out of power units by 2030. The region is also actively engaged in research projects to explore alternatives to mitigate emissions, aligning with global climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts. The "REnewables in Latin America

and the Caribbean" (RELAC) initiative aims to achieve at least 80% participation of renewable energies in the region's electricity consumption by 2030, moreover if the countries have a high percentage of penetration the achieves 90%[2]. Additionally, there are significant developments and policy changes aimed at promoting sustainable growth and social development, evident in the integration of renewable energy sources and technologies, as well as a focus on energy efficiency and reducing energy intensity. The future of the energy sector in the region is firmly aligned with global climate change mitigation efforts, aiming to address environmental concerns while fostering economic growth [3], [4], [5].

- Objective and aims

The aim of this methodological approach is to establish a systematic workflow that enables the harmonization of diverse energy matrices across the 27 countries in Latin America and the Caribbean, thereby streamlining decision-making within a unified system.

2. Methodology

In the field of energy modelling, the development of a sophisticated and robust methodology is essential for effectively navigating the intricacies of integrated energy system analysis, thereby ensuring the precision and reliability of decision-making processes. Figure 1 describes the flow of this process.

Figure 1. Implemented workflow

The workflow implementation requires a manual preprocessing of country-specific data, followed by adherence to the routines of the Integrated System, which are programmed in Python. The initial stage of this process involves a systematic acquisition of data from the Starter Data Kits (SDK). This phase requires a detailed preprocessing of the information. The acquired data is then aligned with the pre-established naming conventions and file structures essential for processing within the OSeMOSYS model framework. This alignment results in the creation of a `data_input` file, containing country-specific data.

The method then advances to the structured and integrated organization of this input data in an Excel format. During this phase, each parameter is meticulously classified on separate sheets, rendering the data ready for integration into the OSeMOSYS framework. Following this, the data undergoes parameterization and conversion into the MathProg file format, ensuring its compatibility with the CPLEX solver. The choice of the commercially licensed CPLEX solver, used here for academic purposes, is due to its superior performance compared to the freely available GLPK solver, especially for large-scale problems.

Subsequently, a linear programming file (.lp) is constructed and processed through the chosen solver. The output is then converted into a comma-separated values (.csv) file, utilizing functions from the *otoole* library. The final stages of the workflow include the automated generation of visualizations.

Regarding the strategic expansion of the energy integration model, it is planned to proceed in stages. Initially, the integration will incorporate Colombia and Ecuador, leveraging their geographical proximity to conduct preliminary commercial tests efficiently. The model will then be extended to the other Andean nations, followed by the integration of the Southern Cone countries and Brazil. The initiative will progressively encompass Central America and Mexico and will ultimately conclude with the integration of the Caribbean countries. This phased approach is designed to ensure a comprehensive and systematic integration of the energy matrices across the Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) region.

3. Results

The Figure 3 chart illustrates a remarkable growth in the energy sector, with onshore wind technology experiencing a rapid increase. This growth aligns with the Figure 4 chart, where onshore wind and medium hydro technologies show substantial contributions to the power output. Notably, the reliance on coal remains significant, suggesting a diversified but carbon-intensive energy mix.

Figure 2. Installed Capacity for Ecuador

Figure 3. Installed capacity for Colombia.

Conversely, Figure 2 presents a balanced expansion across several renewable technologies, notably hydro and onshore wind, with solar showing a steady rise. This diversification is echoed in Figure 5, where the growth in hydro and wind power generation is evident, indicating a strong shift towards renewable energy. The Figure 5 showcases a steep upward trajectory in energy production from onshore wind

technology, indicating a significant shift towards harnessing wind as a key power source.

Figure 4. Power generation for Colombia.

Figure 5. Power generation for Ecuador.

The cooperation benefits chart further (Figure 6) underscores the cost-effectiveness of collaborative approaches to energy policy and infrastructure development. The difference between individual and cooperative costs highlights the economic advantages of shared initiatives and strategic partnerships in the energy sector.

Figure 6. Cooperation benefits at costs.

4. Discussion

The methodological approach adopted in this study facilitates an initial comparison of the energy matrices of Colombia (COL) and Ecuador (ECU). Analysis of the data reveals that both nations are progressing significantly in the realm of renewable energies, albeit with distinct strategies and facing unique challenges. Colombia's substantial investment in wind energy, juxtaposed with its ongoing reliance on coal, signifies a transitional phase towards cleaner energy sources. Policy-wise, Colombia could potentially benefit from measures aimed at phasing out older coal plants and enhancing energy storage solutions to support the intermittency of renewable sources.

Ecuador's investment in renewable energy, characterized by a more balanced distribution across different technologies, reflects a strategic commitment to energy security and sustainability. ECU may further strengthen its energy portfolio by integrating geothermal and biomass technologies. Moreover, as the cooperation benefits chart indicates, both countries stand to gain from regional collaboration. Joint efforts in policy development and infrastructure investment can lead to cost reductions and enhanced efficiency.

However, there are limitations to this methodological approach. One significant constraint is the limited hardware capacity, particularly in terms of RAM, necessary for analyzing the energy matrices of the 27 countries in Latin America and the Caribbean. For this exercise, the analysis was confined to two countries, which itself presented a considerable processing challenge. Additionally, issues were identified in some Starter Data Kits (SDKs), necessitating a thorough review of this foundational data before it can be fully integrated. Another limitation lies in the reliance on commercial solvers to efficiently process models with extensive data, a factor that needs to be reconciled with the goal of adhering to open-source initiatives.

In terms of potential interventions and implementation challenges, this system is intended to be integrated into the global OSeMOSYS initiative. Currently, OSeMOSYS focuses primarily on the power system, but plans are underway to enhance the efficiency of trading routes beyond current capabilities. This is part of a larger vision for a globally integrated and robust system that encompasses all aspects of the power system. This broader perspective underscores the need for continued development and refinement of the methodologies and tools used in energy system analysis.

5. Conclusions

The establishment of an automated workflow has been instrumental in analyzing the energy profiles of Colombia and Ecuador under a trend scenario. This analysis underscores each country's active commitment to renewable technologies, albeit through distinct national strategies. Colombia's emphasis on wind energy, contrasted with Ecuador's more diversified approach, exemplifies the dynamic evolution of the region's energy transition. The evident economic advantages of collaborative efforts suggest that regional joint policies and investments in energy infrastructure can significantly expedite the transition towards a sustainable and economically viable energy landscape in Latin America.

The implementation of a comprehensive integrated system for managing the entire energy framework of Latin America and the Caribbean is critical. This system will not only identify but also guide the establishment of essential policies needed for effective implementation. Working in unison at a regional level enables the achievement of energy objectives more cost-effectively.

The benefits of enhanced cooperation and energy exchange are manifold. By leveraging the unique natural resources of each country, significant mutual benefits can be realized. Such collaboration leads to optimized resource utilization, enhancing the overall energy efficiency and sustainability of LAC nations.

The approach identifies clear win-win opportunities for all involved parties. By aligning their energy policies and strategies, countries within the region can create synergies that not only bolster their individual energy sectors but also contribute to regional stability and growth. These synergies pave the way for a more resilient and interconnected energy network, offering economic, environmental, and social advantages.

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